

Heterocyclic Systems with Bridgehead Nitrogen Atom : Reactions of 4-Amino-5-mercapto-3-substituted-*s*-triazoles with Haloketones and 2,3-Dichloroquinoxaline

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Condensation of 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-alkyl-*s*-triazole (I) with chloranil and α -haloketones furnished 3,10-dimethyl-6,13-dichloro bis (*s*-triazolo [3,4-*b*] [1,3,4] thiadiazine [5,6-*b*:5',6'-*e*] cyclohexa-1,4-diene(II) and 7*H*-3,6-disubstituted-*s*-triazolo [3,4-*b*] [1,3,4] thiadiazines(VI) respectively. Similarly reaction of I with 2,3-dichloro quinoxaline afforded 5*H*-*s*-triazolo [3,4-*b*] [1,3,4] thiadiazino [5,6-*b*] quinoxaline(IV). Compound II is a hitherto unknown and novel heterocyclic system.

IN continuation of our work on the syntheses of bridgehead nitrogen heterocycles¹⁻³, syntheses of 3,10-dimethyl-6,13-dichloro bis (*s*-triazolo [3,4-*b*] [1,3,4] thiadiazino[5,6-*b*:5',6'-*e*] cyclohexa-1,4-diene(II), 5*H*-3-ethyl-*s*-triazolo-[3,4-*b*] [1,3,4] thiadiazino [5,6-*b*] quinoxaline (IV) and 7*H*-3,6-disubstituted-*s*-triazolo [3,4-*b*] [1,3,4] thiadiazines(VI) have been accomplished and are presented in this communication.

reveals that compound (II) is a hitherto unknown and novel heterocyclic system. Reaction of I (R = C₂H₅) with 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline in presence of anhydrous ethanol and fused sodium acetate afforded the heterocycle (IV). Following the method of Hoggarth⁷ some new triazolo thiadiazines (V) have been synthesized by reacting triazoles (I) with certain α -haloketones. The spectral character of compounds II, IV, V and VI are also consistent with the

CHART I

1. 2,3-Dichloroquinoxaline, EtOH;
2. Chloranil, NaOAc, CH₂COH/DMF; 3. R₁COCH₂X, EtOH
4. NH₃.

The reaction of chloranil with *o*-amino-thiophenole^{4,5} and *o*-aminophenols⁶ have been reported. Similar condensation of chloranil with the triazole (I, R = CH₃) gave a compound which was assigned by the structure II and not by III on the basis of IR spectral and analytical data. The absence of absorption in the region 1680-1700 cm⁻¹ is in good agreement with the structure II. A survey of literature

structures proposed for them (vide experimental). Compounds (IV and V) were found to possess no activity at 1:1000 concentration when tested⁸ against *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Candida albicans*, *Microsporum gypsum* and *Trichophyton ratinum*.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected, I. R. spectra were taken in Nujol mull.

3, 10-Dimethyl-6, 13-dichloro bis (*s*-triazolo[3, 4-*b*] [1, 3, 4] thiadiazino [5, 6-*b*: 5', 6'-*e*]) cyclo hexa-1,4-diene(II).

(a) A solution of the triazole (I, R=CH₃)⁹ (2.60 g. 0.02 mole) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) was added to a solution of chloranil (2.48 g, 0.01 mole) and anhydrous sodium acetate (1.64 g, 0.02 mole) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) and the mixture refluxed for about 3 hrs. The reaction mixture acquired reddish colouration and a red solid started separating after about 15-20 minutes. On cooling, the red coloured solid was filtered, washed thoroughly with water in order to remove sodium acetate, then with little ethenol and finally recrystallized from DMF. The compound (II) (1.8 g, 45%) had m. p. >280°. ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) 1650, 1540, 1155, 925, 835, 690 (Found: C, 36.02; H, 1.65; S, 15.93 Calcd, for C₁₂H₈N₄S₂Cl₂. C, 36.27; H, 1.51; S, 16.12%).

7H-6-Biphenyl-3-ethyl-*s*-triazolo [3, 4-*b*] [1, 3, 4] thiadiazine (VI, R=C₂H₅; R₁=C₆H₅-C₆H₄)

II (R=C₂H₅, 0.72 g, 0.005 mole), *p*-phenacyl bromide (1.35g, 0.005 mole) in anhydrous ethanol (20ml) was refluxed for about 6 hrs. The solid obtained on cooling was crystallized from ethanol to afford colourless micro needles m.p. 211 yield 1.5g (75%). (Found: S, 7.49; N, 13.72 Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₇N₄S Br. S, 7.98; N, 13.96%).

The above hydrobromide (0.5 g) was dissolved in ethanol and ammonia solution was added dropwise till alkaline and kept for some time, when colourless crystals separated. m. p. 222° ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) 1610, 1535, 720, 690. (Found: S, 9.72; N, 17.24 Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₆N₄S. S, 10.00; N, 17.50%).

The properties and analyses of other *s*-triazolo-thiadiazines are described in Table 1.

TABLE 1 7H-3-ALKYL-6-ARYL-*s*-TRIAZOLO [3,4-*b*] [1,3,4] THIADIAZINE HYDROHALIDES (V)

R	R ₁	X	m.p.°C.	Yield %	Formula	%Sulphur	
						Found	Calcd.
H	3,4(OH) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	Cl	270 (decomp.)	58	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ SO ₂ Cl	10.94	11.25
CH ₃	3,4(OH) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	Cl	266	80	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ SO ₂ Cl†	10.43	10.72
CH ₃	2,3,4, (OH) ₃ C ₆ H ₂	Cl	275*	75	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ SO ₂ Cl††	9.86	10.17
CH ₃	<i>p</i> NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	Br	270*	65	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ SO ₂ Br	8.57	8.99
CH ₃	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ -C ₆ H ₄	Br	256	84	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ S Br	8.04	8.27
C ₂ H ₅	2,3,4 (OH) ₃ C ₆ H ₂	Cl	240 (decomp.)	70	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₄ SO ₂ Cl	9.48	9.74
C ₂ H ₅	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	Br	223	50	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₄ S Br Cl	8.53	8.90
C ₃ H ₇	2,3,4(OH) ₃ C ₆ H ₂	Cl	215	53	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₄ SO ₂ Cl†††	9.12	9.34

*Charring Takes place.
IR frequencies

+ 3320-3240, 1620, 1520, 1020, 810.
†† 3300, 1630, 1520, 1010, 790.
††† 3320-3160, 1630, 1510, 910, 795.

(b) Compound (I, R=CH₃, 0.02 mole) and chloranil (0.01 mole) were dissolved separately in hot dimethylformamide and mixed the two in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate (0.02 mole) and the reaction mixture kept for 48 hrs. The red coloured solid thus obtained was filtered, washed with water and crystallized from DMF. m.p. >280°. Its IR spectrum was superimposable with that of sample obtained by method (a).

5H-3-Ethyl-*s*-triazolo [3, 4-*b*] [1,3,4] thiadiazino [5, 6-*b*] quinoxaline (IV).

The triazole (I, R=C₂H₅)⁹ (0.72 g, 0.005 mole), 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline (1.00 g, 0.005 mole) and fused sodium acetate (0.82 g) in anhydrous ethanol (25ml) were refluxed or a steam bath for about 6 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled and the separated yellow solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallized from ethanol to afford the quinoxaline (IV) (0.70 g, 50%) in yellow micro needles, m.p. 158°. ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹) 3040, 1620, 1535, 1275, 1190, 995, 765. (Found: S, 11.49; N, 30.92 Calcd. for C₁₂H₁₀N₄S. S, 11.85; N, 31.11%).

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References

- V. K. CHADHA, H. S., CHAUDHARY and H. K. PUJARI, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1969, 22, 2697.
- V. K. CHADHA, *Ann. Soc. Sci. Bruxelles*, 1977, 91, 101.
- K. S. DHAKA, J. MOHAN, V. K. CHADHA and H. K. PUJARI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, 12, 966, 485.
- M. A. ALBERT, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 1976, 13, 1067.
- S. K. SAXENA, A. P. SHUKLA, M. D. SADHANANI and R. L. MITTAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14B, 808.
- N. L. AGGARWAL and R. L. MITTAL, *J. Inst. Chemists (India)*, 1976, 48, 180.
- E. HOGGARTH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4811.
- R. S. C. AYTOUN, A. H. CAMPBELL, E. J. NAPIER and D. A. L. SCILLER, *Arch. Derm. Syph.*, 1960, 81, 650.
- H. SAJKACHI and M. KANAOKA, *Yakugaku Zasshi*, 1962, 82, 683; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1963, 58, 4543.